

SCHOOL VARIABLES, CYBERBULLYING AS PREDICTORS OF SOCIAL RESTIVENESS AMONG UNIVERSITY UNDERGRADUATES IN RIVERS STATE: IMPLICATION FOR COUNSELLING

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Abstract

This study investigated school variables, cyberbullying as predictors of social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State. Three research questions and three corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The research design for this study was correlational design. The estimated population for this study was 35,000 university undergraduates in Rivers State. This estimation was because as at the time of this study there was no accurate figure in any government department housing the population of elderly in Rivers State. The sample size of this study comprised 500 university undergraduates in Rivers State. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. Two instruments titled: "School Variables and Cyberbullying Scale" (SVACS) and "Social Restiveness Inventory" (SRI)" was used for data collection. The instruments (SVACS) and (SRI) were validated based on face and content validities by experts. Cronbach alpha reliability statistics was used to compute the general reliability coefficient of (SVACS) to be 0.77 and (SRI) to be 0.79. Simple regression was used to answer research question 1-3 and their corresponding hypotheses was also tested at 0.05 Alpha level of significance. The findings of the study show that: school policies, peer association and cyberbullying significantly predicted social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State. Based on the findings of this study conclusion, recommendations and implications for counselling were made.

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Introduction

It is uncommon to see any society that has not recorded social restiveness, this perhaps is because conflicts are bound to occur, these conflict takes place between people of all ages groups, ethnic, religion or race. In Nigeria social restiveness among undergraduates has become an issue of concern. In today's contemporary society university undergraduates have been observed to be involved in social restive behaviour that have endangered not only their lives, but the lives of other people who reside in the school community. These undergraduates of different universities believed that engaging in social restive behaviour may bring liberation. There has been an increase in the occurrence of acts of violence and lawlessness, like vandalization of public property, hostage-taking of prominent citizens and resource person, illegal oil bunkering, arms insurgence, cultism, etc. Undergraduates who are youths that are usually between the age of 16-35 are endowed with natural energy, their energy are the reason for thier high enthusiastic spirit, high hopes, big dreams, unmatched aspiration, and appealing ideas of what the future owes them. This nature of theirs propels them to be disturbed, become anxious and engage in activities that helps to fast track their future. Thus, a little disappointment in relation to the attainment of their aspiration, as well as their individual and collective goals usually triggers the propensity for violence which often times metamorphose to restiveness (Ogbefune 2013). Undergraduates who are not properly groomed by the socialization agents like the family, religious bodies, institutions of learning, mass media, political party, pressure groups, have been observed to display socially unacceptable behaviour. Onyene (2017) asserted that being restive refers to the act of being unable to stay and remain still. It is the unwillingness to adhere to any form of control as a result of boredom or dissatisfaction about occurrences, decisions, laws, rules and regulations that may be perceived to be detrimental. Undergraduates who are uninformed are willing tools in the hands of people who perpetrate mischief. People who master- mind restive activities for their selfish gain, oftentimes engage university undergraduates in their skim with the promise of giving them certain jobs, appointment or remuneration. Undergraduate restiveness can take the form of riot, protest and vandalism, which ever form that is displayed, swift intervention must be carried out by the school security to instill peace. U undergraduate's restiveness etiologically are politically, socially, religiously and economically motivated (Akunne et al., 2018). Sulieman (2019) asserted that youth restive and violence behaviour leaves the youth in a hostile social situation, especially when the boundaries between legal and illegal, legitimate and illegitimate are very much unclear.

Aborisade and Adebayo (2018) opined that social media which is mostly used by undergraduates exposes them to violence such as cyberbullying, gang violence, and self-directed violence. Social media violence that increasingly occurs in the internet plays an important role in prevalence and spread of violent and social restive behaviour in tertiary institution of learning and in our beloved country Nwosu et al., (2018). In many nation's of the earth, there are increasing cases of cyberbullying, studies have demonstrated that the detrimental effects of cyberbullying affects the mental health of both victims and standbys. It was observed that not much has been done in the Nigerian context to document the incidence of social restiveness among Nigerian undergraduates in spite of the alarming rate of nternet misuse. In the era of digitalization, there is the availability of ICT gadgets like smartphones, laptops, desktops, tablets, etc. These gadgets has transformed physical bullying into cyberbullying and has made undergraduates to use social media platforms to express their anger and perform activity that will lead to social restiveness.

Tokunaga (2010) asserted that cyberbullying is any bullying behaviour performed over electronic media by Individual(s) who repeatedly disseminate messages that are intended to cause trouble, catastrophe or harm to others meant. Rahman et al. (2021) in his study on university students found out that social media, exposes

students or young people to cyber harassment. Cyberbullying have numerous types, these types include flaming hurtful and insulting messages at people, sending messages of harassment, publishing secret and sensitive information, misinforming people, sending sexual and erotic messages, pictures and videos, etc. (Newey & Magson, 2010).

Studies have demonstrated that that cyberbullying predicts victimization, restiveness hostile health and psychological problems (Koyanagi et al., 2019). Undergraduates are socially connected via internet connections. However, the internet have become a breeding ground for cyberbullying. Technologies are a blessing for society if it is not used to generates series of psychological health problems that can potentially lead to social restiveness, social isolation, depression and scholastic maladjustmet that may turn into suicidal tendencies (Lee & Wu, 2018).

School variables which includes factors that are present in the institution of learning may also predict social restiveness. Uriah and Ololube (2011) asserted that funding of the universities and the policies adopted by the school senate and governing body impedes undergraduate learning experience. Also, sequel to the non-exposure to adequate information and communication technology, healthy environment, uninterrupted power supply, quality health care and other essential facilities triggers undergraduate's restiveness. Akunne et al (2021) opined that school policies which is enshrined in school variables can contribute to undergraduate's restiveness especially when the rules and regulations guiding the institution of learning are perceived to be witch hunting them, these students may result to protest, and vandalization of school property, rioting and other anti-social activities

Another school variables that may predict social restiveness is peer association. It is observed in the university that friends associated with and their behaviour, attitude, as well rules and regulations made by freinds may also trigger social restive behaviour. Peer association also known as peer group association is defined as the social class in which undergraduates with similar characteristics interact with each other. Via peer association and interaction ideas are formed and shared among undergraduates. Igho and Ikpa (2013) noted that peer association has a lot of influence on the lives of fellow peers. This perhaps may be because peer association may determine university undergraduates talk, walk behave or wear. Peer association form an integral part of an undergraduates life inside and off campus, it has been observed to Influence the way and manner in which they interact among themselves and also how they handle events or policies that seem to be detrimental to their physical or mental well-being. It is against this background that the researcher envisaged the need to investigate school variables, cyberbullying as predictors of social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Review of Literature

One of the many-sided effects of environmental injustice is "social restiveness" which metamorphosed into the purchase and use of arms and the emergence of militants that is no doubt a threat to the university community and to the Nigerian macro environment. Social restiveness includes protesting against constituted authority, and engaging in activities that will treathen the peace of people living in the university and it's environs.

Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) explains how undergraduates learn to behave aggressively by watching the aggressive behaviour of others on various social media platforms. Aduba (2019) stated that the restiveness level of undergraduates is heightened when they perceive that their future is about to be joepodized. Dua (2019) highlights improper socialization, family problems, political, social and economic inequalities, defective, educational system, unemployment, underemployment, corrupt and discredited authority, misuse of student power by the school administration, administrative failures gap in communication, differences in values,

lack of opportunities, discrepancy between aspirations and achievements, lack of determination and focus, self-responsibility and Influence of media are factors that contribute to social restiveness among undergraduates.

Nuate and Oyindo (2022) in their study focused on social and demographic factors as determinant of secondary school student's participation in social restive activities in Ogoni, Rivers State. The researchers adopted a descriptive research design, seven research questions and hypothesis guided the study. Findings of the study showed that peer affiliation ($p=0.36>0.05$) did not have any influence on restiveness. Ezeji (2020) evaluated the influence of social media on youth restiveness in Nigeria. The study adopted qualitative methodology. The findings revealed that Cyberbullying escalates into violence, and restiveness.

Ezedikachi, (2020) examined youth restiveness and its impact on the economic development in Nigeria using Niger-Delta as a study. The study used the relative deprivation and the broken window theories as the theoretical framework. The research adopted qualitative method. Findings showed that the nature of most youths that engage in youth restive activities in the Niger-Delta do not have access to formal education; these youths are majorly unemployed and poor and this may not have access to information communication gadgets. Ezeaku and Dunu (2020) examined the role of education in managing social vices and youth restiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions were answered and a null hypothesis was tested. The study revealed that a defective education policy promotes social restiveness among students. Daniel (2019) examines the causes, the manifestation, consequences and ways of curbing youth restiveness in the eastern senatorial district of Kogi state. The paper reveals that drug abuse and youth restiveness are caused by peer group influence.

Statement of the Problem

Social restiveness and other form of violence are not new in Rivers State. Undergraduates in Rivers State irrespective of the higher institution attended seem to be engaged in social restive activities. These activities has caused rancor to academic and non-academic activities and has resulted to a university problems that affects, the school community, people who reside close to the institution. Undergraduates in Rivers State has been observed to be so engrossed with their mobile phones, laptops and other ICT gadget such that they use it to bully other students by either sharing their private information or forcing them to do their biddings. Undergraduates have also been observed to incite problems and controversy among other students via cyberbullying.

Also, school policies that are not conducive or unfavourable has also been observed to foster disunity among student union leaders and the school administrations, this has led to school riot, vandalizing of school properties, institution based strike and sometimes if not controlled can cause social restiveness

It was also observed that peers in their quest for supremacy and attention have also been observed to create pressure groups who go heads on with other groups, lecturers and other school administration thereby leading to social restiveness and other form of social vices in Rivers State. In other to contribute towards the control of social restiveness among undergraduates the researcher therefore deemed it necessary to examine school variables, cyberbullying as predictors of social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate school variables, cyberbullying as predictors of social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State. The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To investigate the extent to which university polices predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State

2. To investigate the extent to which peer association predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.
3. To investigate the extent to which cyberbullying predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide this study.

1. To what extent does university polices predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State
2. To what extent does peer association predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does cyberbullying predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance were used to guide this study.

1. University policies does not significantly predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.
2. Peer association does not significantly predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.
3. Cyberbullying does not significantly predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Methodology

The research design for this study was correlational design. The estimated population for this study was 35,000 university undergraduates in Rivers State. This estimation was because as at the time of this study there was no accurate figure in any government department housing the population of the entire university undergraduates in Rivers State. The sample size of this study comprised 500 university undergraduates. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. Two instruments titled: "School Variables and Cyberbullying Scale" (SVACS) and "Social Restiveness Inventory" (SRI) was used for data collection. The (SVACS) and (SRI) comprised 24 items each. All the items were structured based on the four point modified likert rating scale of Strongly Agree = SA, agreed = A, disagree = D and Strongly Disagree = SD which were assigned numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 for positively keyed items and 1, 2, 3 and 4 for negatively keyed items. The instruments (SVACS) and (SRI) were validated based on face and content validities by three experts; one in guidance and counselling and two others in measurement and evaluation. To establish reliability a sample of 30 undergraduates from Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic who were not part of the sample for this study were administered the questionnaire, cronbach alpha reliability statistics was used to compute the general reliability coefficient of (SVACS) to be 0.77 and (SRI) to be 0.79. The researcher engaged the services of (student union leaders) in all these universities who were properly guided on what to do and the instruments were retrieved immediately after administration. However only 499 copies were retrieved from the respondents. Simple regression was used to answer research question 1-3 and their corresponding hypotheses was also tested at 0.05 Alpha level of significance.

Results

The results of this study were presented in the tables as follows:

Research Question One: To what extent does university polices predict social restiiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State?

Hypothesis One: University policies does not significantly predict social restiiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Table 1: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Prediction of University Policies and Social Restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Decision
1	.168 ^a	.063	6.59928	Mid Prediction

Source: SPSS Output, 2023

Table 1 shows that there is a moderate positive relation between university policies and social restiveness among undergraduates R=0.168. The adjusted R square value=0.063. This implies that 4.3% of the social restive behaviour among university undergraduates can be explained by university policies while the remaining 95.7 % can be due to other factors not included in this model.

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on University Policies and Social Restiveness among University undergraduates in Rivers State

Source	Sum of Squares (SS)	Df	Mean Square	F. Ratio	P-value	Remark
Regression	547.971	1	547.971	9875	.002	S
Residual	18213.113	498	43.551			
Total	18761.084	499				

Linear R (r_p) =.168^a

R. Square (r^2) =.063

Standard Error of Estimate =6.59928

Source: SPSS Output, 2023.

Table 2: shows that for every increase by 1SD in the university policies score, there will be an increase of 0.15 SD in the scores of social restiveness among university undergraduates.

a. Dependent Variable: social restiveness scores

b. Predictors: (Constant), school policies

The coefficient table shows that the prediction is significant (F=9.88, DF=1, 498, p<0.05), hence HO1 which state that school policies significantly predict social restiveness among undergraduates therefore the hypotheses is rejected.

Research Question Two: To what extent does peer association and social restiiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State?

Hypothesis Two: Peer association does not significantly predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Prediction of Peer Association and Social Restiveness among University undergraduates in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Decision
1	.716 ^a	.079	6.60654	High Prediction

Source: SPSS Output, 2023 a. Dependent Variable: social restiveness b. predictors: (constant), peer association
 Table 3 shows that there is a very high relationship between peer association and social restiveness (R= 0.716)
 The Adjusted R square value= 0.79 shows that only 79% of the social restiveness among undergraduates can be explained by peer association. The remaining 21% in the social restive behaviour of university undergraduates can be attributed to other factors not included in the model.

Table 4: Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analysis on the Prediction of Peer Association and Social Restiveness among University undergraduates in Rivers State

Source	Sum of Squares (SS)	Df	Mean Square	F. Ratio	P-value	Remark
Regression	416.979	1	416.979	9575.2	.003	S
Residual	17333.113	498	43.551			
Total	17750.092	499				

Linear R (r_p) = .716^a

R. Square (r^2) = .079

Standard Error of Estimate =6.60654

Source: SPSS Output, 2023. a. Dependent Variable: social restiveness b. Predictors: (Constant), peer association

The coeficient table shows that the prediction is significant (F= 9575.2, DF=1, 498, p<0.05). Therefore, HO2 is rejected, implying that peer association significantly predicts social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Research Question Three: To what extent does cyberbullying and social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State?

Hypothesis Three: Cyberbullying does not significantly predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Table 5: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Prediction of Cyberbullying and Social Restiveness among University undergraduates in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Decision
1	.621 ^a	.637	5.20843	Moderate Prediction

Source: SPSS Output, 2023 a. Dependent Variable: Social restiveness b. Predictors: (Constant), cyberbullying
 Table 3 shows that there is a positive moderate relationship between cyberbullying and social restiveness among undergraduates (R= 0.621). With an adjusted R-square value of 0.637, it implies that 63.7% of the variation in social restiveness can be explained by cyberbullying behaviour among university undergraduates while the remaining 36.3% can be due to other factors not included in this model.

Table 6; Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analysis on the Prediction on Cyberbullying and Social Restiveness among University undergraduates in Rivers State

Source	Sum of Squares (SS)	Df	Mean Square	F. Ratio	P-value	Remark
Regression	6957.532	1	6957.532	267.575	.004	S
Residual	10793.560	498	27.117			
Total	17860.093	499				

Linear R (r_p) =.621^a

R. Square (r^2) =.637

Standard Error of Estimate =5.20843

Source: SPSS Output, 2023. a. Dependent Variable: Social restiveness scores b. Predictors: (Constant), cyberbullying

Table 6 shows that for every increase by 1 SD in the cyberbullying scores there will be an increase of 0.15 SD in the social restiveness among university undergraduates.

Table 6 shows that the prediction is significant ($F= 267.58$, $df=1, 498$, $p<0.05$), hence H_03 is rejected. This implies that cyberbullying significantly predicts social restiveness among undergraduates in the university.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study are summarized as shown below:

1. It was found that university policy significantly independently predicted social restiveness among university undergraduates.
2. It was found that peer association significantly independently predicted social restiveness among university undergraduates.
3. The study showed that cyberbullying significantly independently predicts social restiveness among university undergraduates.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings was based on summary of the findings of this study. The finding of research questions one and its corresponding hypothesis one revealed that university policy significantly independently predicted social restiveness among university undergraduates. This means the policies that are implemented in the university may trigger social restiveness among undergraduates. This finding is in agreement with that of Ezeaku and Dunu (2020) who revealed that defective education policies promote social restiveness among university students.

The finding of research question two and hypothesis two showed that peer association significantly independently predicted social restiveness among university undergraduates. This also implies that peer association which is usually accompanied with peer pressure affects how undergraduates react to frustration or feelings that their future is about to be trampled upon. This finding is in agreement with that of Daniel (2019) who found out that social restiveness is caused by peer group influence. The finding is also in disagreement with Nuata and Oyindo (2022) whose findings showed that peer association did not have any influence on social restiveness.

The finding of research questions three and hypothesis three indicated that cyberbullying significantly independently predicts social restiveness among university undergraduates. This means that cyberbullying which is a negative use of ICT gadgets and social media affects the mood, personality and perception of undergraduate students and thus triggers them to resort into social restiveness. This finding is in line with that of Ezeji (2020) who found that cyberbullying escalates into violence, and restiveness. The findings of this study are also in disagreement with Ezedikachi, (2020) who revealed that undergraduates are majorly unemployed and poor and thus may not have access to information communication gadgets.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that school policies, peer association and cyberbullying significantly predict social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State. Therefore, school variables and cyberbullying play an important role in the emergence of social restiveness among university undergraduates in Rivers State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

1. Despite the fact that peer affiliation is not the only factor that predict restiveness, the researcher recommended that teachers, gaurdain parents and counselors should watch out for the type of friends that their children wards and students keep.
2. It is recommended that parents, lecturers as well as the guidance counselor should endeavour to sensitize and re-sensitize undergraduates on the pros and cons of cyberbullying, seminar and webinars on the appropriate usage of ICT gadgets should be carried out in the school community.
3. Counselors should pay more attention to students plight and also advocate for students to be heard and considered when decisions and policies that will affect them directly or otherwise are been made .

Implications for Counselling

The following are the counselling implications of the findings of this study:

1. There is a need for the provision of free addictive and educative counselling programs that will address the issue of cyberbullying by the guidance-counsellors in our society.
2. Counselling services should be tailored towards the management of peer pressure and its influence on the decision making and lifestyle of students at all levels.
3. Counselling services should be provided to students who thinks or perceives that the university policies are geared towards distorting their future.
4. The guidance counsellor in collaboration with the government and other agencies should sensitize members of the general public on the best ways to help address issues of social restiveness in the school environment. How to prevent the escalation of social restiveness in the school community and in Nigeria's macro environment should also be disseminated.

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